

THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL VIRTUES IN THE EDUCATION OF A PERFECT HUMAN BEING IN THE WORKS OF ORIENTAL THINKERS

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***Abstract.** This article talks about the ideas of Oriental thinkers about perfect human education. Also, knowledge and correct use of methods of manners and ethics in child upbringing from the point of view of o thinkers. information about their spiritual heritage and pedagogical activity is given.*

***Keywords:** perfect person, moral rules, manners, education, spirituality, moral qualities, national values.*

While we focus on the issues of perfect human education in the works of Eastern thinkers, in the **introduction** of the article we make sure that the formation of spiritual and moral qualities is a problem of special importance. "Truly, the root of every development depends on the development of science and education," says the head of our state Sh. Mirziyoev.

The spiritual heritage left by our ancestors is of great importance in the education of the young generation. Our nation has long been known to the world for its intelligence and knowledge. Its proof can be seen in the works of great scientists who devoted their lives to the development of science. If we look at the history, no matter how many, how precious and incomparable the material wealth is, one day they may age and disappear under the influence of some event, but we can witness that the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors has not lost its value over the centuries.

Although the cultural-spiritual heritage is different from each other, we should not put an impenetrable "Chinese" wall between them, the basis of the establishment of cultural heritage is spirituality, that is, the cultural-spiritual knowledge, ability, talent, mind and theoretical knowledge activity of a person. Of course, there are similarities and differences between cultural and spiritual heritage.

Spiritual wealth is inherited from generation to generation, from one system to another, and society and the state greatly influence its spiritual development.

In this regard, in **the theoretical part** of the article, the term "spiritual heritage" refers to universal spiritual wealth of the distant and recent past, of the present, which is spiritually valuable, leaves an indelible mark, lives forever, and serves the good of all social interests and needs.

Our nation is considered one of the nations that made a great contribution to the development of the world. Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Motrudi, Najmuddin Kubra, Mahmud Zamakhshari Bahauddin Naqshband, famous scholars such as Ahmad Farghani, Muhammad Khorazmi, Ibn Sina, Abu Raykhan Beruni, Mirza Ulughbek Abu Great poets and thinkers such as Nasr Farobi, Alisher Navoi, Boborahim Mashrab, Abdulla Avloni, Ogahi made a worthy contribution to the advancement of science and knowledge, and the education of a perfect human being, and left behind a rich spiritual legacy.

The rich and priceless national spiritual heritage of our great-grandfathers instills in the hearts of today's young students education, morality, humanity, honesty and other noble human qualities.

The first president of our country I.A. In one of his works, Karimov said: "The spiritual heritage left by our ancestors is a huge treasure. We should use this treasure wisely to strengthen our independence."

In the practical part of the article, the merits of the great saint Imam Bukhari in human education and perfection are great. Imam Bukhari left a legacy of invaluable and valuable knowledge to the generations, the number of works he wrote is more than twenty. One of the most famous of them is the work "Al-Jome' as sahih", which is considered the second most important source of religion. In his writings, Imam Bukhari thinks about manners and morals, calls to respect parents and fulfill one's duties towards the society. He calls people to be honest, truthful and fulfill their promises. According to him, he shows three signs of a hypocrite:

1. Lying; 2. Breach of promise; 3. Betrayal of deposit.

Although the work "Al-Jame' As-Sahih" was written 1200 years ago, it has not lost its value to this day. The hadiths mentioned in this work of Imam Bukhari are true human qualities such as kindness, generosity, respect for parents, respect for teachers, care for the poor and needy, kindness for orphans. There is also room for self-love, hard work and honesty. In this book, instruction and propaganda are important for the people of our society today, especially for the education of the younger generation. According to researches, 2327 copies of Al-Jome'As-Sahih manuscript are kept in complete parts in 2327 libraries of the world. There are 226 original copies of this book in Abdulaziz Madina Munawwara Library. Our people say that young people are always the backbone of the nation. A country that thinks about its future, first of all, pays attention to the education of young people. Both body and soul need constant cultivation. Therefore, education is the main issue in the healthy and mature development of a person.

Family is the first source of child education. The role of parents, relatives and society in the education of children and adolescents is very important. If the family is healthy, the children's thinking and behavior in life will be healthy, and the whole society will be healthy. Teenagers in the family should grow up in a peaceful and healthy environment and receive the first education from the family. Because the family is the first school of human education, through which a person finds his place and status in society. If a family brings up their child in the spirit of love, humanity, loyalty to the Motherland, this feeling will remain in his heart for the rest of his life.

In the traditions of Oriental thinkers, the issues of education and upbringing, especially family upbringing, are given a wide place. Those who consider child education as the main task that determines the fate of the society, the future of the people and the nation. In particular, Abdurauf Fitrat in his work "The Way of Salvation" says that every child receives the first education from the mother. This work of Abdurauf Fitrat is a work of great educational value for the young generation. The author sees the destiny of the nation and its happiness in the maturity of family relations in the society. The personality of every person is formed from a young age and accompanies him throughout his life. That's why they try to educate polite, well-educated, honest, educated young people in the society. Factors influencing youth education are positive and negative education. Even a healthy born person can be physically and mentally handicapped as a result of bad upbringing.

The most effective way to combat these factors is knowledge and enlightenment. Therefore, we should pay more attention to the quality of education and training of young people, both the body and the soul of a person always need care, because education is considered as the main task in the healthy and mature growth of the young generation.

One of the famous Persian-Tajik philosophers is Muhammad ibn Zakriya Razi. He is one of the great thinkers who made an incomparable contribution to the development of science, education and our national culture. The basis of Razi's works is education about man. The thinker researches oppression, inequality, injustice, immorality, lies and other features and emphasizes their elimination for the sake of social morality. Abu Bakr Razi emphasized the virtue of manners in his era and said, "Allah Almighty has given man the mind, and through it every man can achieve greatness." Many scholars, including Motrudi from Samarkand, expressed the following opinions about manners in his work "Pandnoma". "There are many fields of knowledge, but they all do their job, but the mind is only a lamp that illuminates the path of human life.

"The meaning of the word "decency" in the dictionary of the Uzbek language: "decency" comes from the Arabic word "adab" and "adab" comes from the Arabic word "good education and good behavior". a person without spirituality cannot occupy a certain position in society and its people.

The development of socio-philosophical ideas of secondary works is associated with the name of the thinker Abu Nasr Farabi, and his teachings about education and training, the perfect person, are of great importance in the field of education and training. Abu Nasr Farab was one of the great scholars and wrote works on all sciences. He was named after the famous Greek philosopher Aristotle in the East with his knowledge and ideas. Scientists say that he created more than 160 scientific works. In his works, the main task is to educate a mature person who can serve the needs of society. In our modern society, education of the younger generation as a perfect person with high qualities characteristic of a mature person in all aspects is taken into account in the state policy. The most effective way to fight against the evils that block the way of the youth today is knowledge and knowledge. In the image of people who have reached the level of a perfect human being, not only the nation, its homeland, but all the good characteristics of the whole humanity can be seen. Abdulla Avloni is one of such figures, who provides religious and secular sciences for the education of the young generation. One of his great works is dedicated to education and training "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics". This work was taught in schools for teaching in a new way in higher grades. At the beginning of the last century, Adullo Awlani's meaningful phrase "Education is a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster for us."

In the years of independence, attention to the field of education in our country has been strengthened. But there are forces all over our country who do not want the future of our Motherland to be among the developed countries of the world, and these forces are trying to influence the young generation, who are the future of our people and nation. attacking the future of our country. Because motherland is introduced to the world by her children who are true patriots. Motherland became sacred thanks to such great and brave people.

Another thinker of great talent is Alisher Navoi. According to Alisher Navoi, knowledge and enlightenment are in the first place. In his opinion, man is the most dear and valuable person in the world. His works spoke about the destiny of the country, loyalty to the motherland, striving for the perfection of human manners, beauty, and love. Indeed, Alisher Navoi's contribution to the

development of science, knowledge, and culture of our nation is very great. His works are a valuable resource for the education of the youth of our country.

To sum up, the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors is the main source of education and upbringing of the people. In this regard, as the President noted: "Happiness is not determined only by the wealth of property. A polite, intelligent, polite, hardworking, believing child is the greatest wealth of a person." The better we know the history and past of our country, the more deeply we will understand the prospects and importance of our peaceful life today, independence, and value every blessing, be it spiritual, cultural, or material. It is not a question of mastering the spiritual and cultural wealth of the past, but of learning it, preserving it, understanding it more deeply, raising it to a new, higher level, and passing it on to the next generation.

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